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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Hydroxychloroquine is an antimalarial and anti-inflammatory drug widely used in the general population, particularly in the treatment of autoimmune diseases.

Case Presentation: Despite its therapeutic benefits, high doses and prolonged use can lead to serious adverse effects, including gastrointestinal disturbances, cardiovascular disorders, dermatological reactions, and retinopathy.

Discussion: Among these, hydroxychloroquine-induced retinopathy is particularly concerning due to its insidious onset and the potential for irreversible vision loss if not detected early.

Conclusion: In this study, we present a case report to evaluate the clinical features of hydroxychloroquine retinopathy, emphasizing the importance of early recognition and regular ophthalmologic screening during long-term therapy.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Hydroxychloroquine, retinopathy, ophthalmology

INTRODUCTION

Hydroxychloroquine (HCQ) is an antimalarial agent widely used in the treatment of autoimmune diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, systemic lupus erythematosus, and Sjögren's syndrome due to its potent anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effects (Nirk, Reggiori, & Mauthe, 2020). Patients often present in the early stages with normal vision or even without any visual symptoms. In advanced stages of the disease, complete vision loss may occur (Modi & Singh, 2019).

Hydroxychloroquine has a toxic effect on the retina depending on the daily dose and duration of use, leading to characteristic 'Bull's-eye maculopathy,' which is characterized by photoreceptor loss and retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) changes in the macula (Mavrikakis et al., 2003; Melles & Marmor, 2014).

In this study, we present a case of retinal toxicity in a patient who had been using hydroxychloroquine long-term for the treatment of Sjögren's syndrome. Informed consent was obtained from the patient.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 62-year-old female patient diagnosed with Sjögren's syndrome presented to our clinic with complaints of blurred vision in both eyes for the past year. She had no history of any ophthalmologic disease, and her best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) was 1.0 bilaterally in an examination conducted four years prior. Upon reviewing her medical history, it was determined that she had been taking 200 mg of oral hydroxychloroquine daily for 14 years for the treatment of Sjögren's syndrome. She had no history of using any other medication. Her BCVA was 0.3 in both the right and left eyes. Intraocular pressure (IOP) was measured as 11.0 mmHg in the right eye and 12.0 mmHg in the left eye. The pupil diameters were normal in both eyes, and both direct and indirect pupillary light reflexes were normal.

Fundoscopy examination revealed a bilateral ring of retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) atrophy surrounding the foveal region, characteristic of "bull's-eye maculopathy."

Fundus autofluorescence (FAF) imaging showed a parafoveal ring with increased fundus hyperautofluorescence and hypoautofluorescence areas corresponding to RPE atrophy in both eyes (Figure 1A, 1B).

Figure 1A

Figure 1B

Optical coherence tomography (OCT) demonstrated parafoveal loss of the ellipsoid zone, along with significant thinning of the external limiting membrane and outer nuclear layer (Figure 2A, 2B).

Figure 3B

Considering the suggestive features of hydroxychloroquine toxicity, the rheumatologist was informed about discontinuing hydroxychloroquine treatment and initiating an alternative medication.

DISCUSSION

The incidence of HCQ retinopathy is approximately 7.5%. The incidence is less than 1% at 5 years and less than 2% at 10 years of use (Melles & Marmor, 2014). Although HCQ retinopathy is often asymptomatic, patients may present with complaints such as blurred vision, central vision loss, photopsias, and metamorphopsia (Gbinigie & Frie, 2020; Marmor et al., 2016; Yam & Kwok, 2006). On clinical examination, abnormalities in the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) develop. In the early stages, bull's-eye maculopathy may occur due to macular edema and/or bilateral granular depigmentation of the RPE in the macula. In the late stages, retinal arteriolar attenuation and optic disc pallor may become more pronounced (Gbinigie & Frie, 2020; Kellner et al., 2014).

According to the latest guidelines from the American Academy of Ophthalmology (AAO), the major risk factors for HCQ retinopathy include an HCQ dose exceeding 5 mg/kg adjusted body weight (ABW) or a chloroquine dose exceeding 2.3 mg/kg ABW, a treatment duration of more than 5 years, renal impairment indicated by reduced glomerular filtration rate (GFR), concomitant tamoxifen use, and pre-existing macular disease (Marmor et al., 2011; Melles & Marmor, 2014).

According to the AAO's latest guidelines, routine screening for HCQ retinopathy involves both visual field testing and spectral-domain optical coherence tomography (SD-OCT). Fundus autofluorescence (FAF) and multifocal electroretinography (mfERG) are also considered useful screening tests. When HCQ is used at an appropriate dosage, the risk of retinopathy remains low within the first 10 years of treatment. Annual screening should commence after 5 years of use if no major risk factors are present. However, in the presence of risk factors, annual screening is recommended regardless of treatment duration (Marmor, Kellner, & Lai, 2016).

CONCLUSION

Hydroxychloroquine-induced retinal toxicity is a serious and irreversible ophthalmic condition. All patients initiating hydroxychloroquine therapy should undergo a baseline ophthalmologic evaluation, followed by

annual examinations after five years of treatment. Patients using hydroxychloroquine without regular follow-up should be referred to an ophthalmology clinic for comprehensive ocular assessment.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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